

MyWaste-Plate

Organisation of Kick-off meeting

Deliverable D1.1

This project has received funding from the European Union, European Health And Digital Executive Agency (HADEA) - Health and Food Directorate under the Grant Agreement SMP-FOOD-2022-FWStakeholders-AG - Project: 101112062 Measurement, reduction, and prevention of food waste in school canteens: proposal of a strategic approach (MYWASTE-PLATE). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DELIVERABLE MYWASTE-PLATE – D1.1

Organization of Kick-off meeting

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Main author	Laura Rossi

Nature of the deliverable		
R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, EU RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIAL or SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgment of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CREA	Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria
Dx.x	Deliverablex.x
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GHGE	greenhouse gas emissions
KoM	Kick Off Meeting
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
WP	Work package

Project abstract

School canteens are considered an essential target for Food Waste (FW) reduction policies combining elements for sustainability education and significant reduction of a relevant source of wastage since the huge amount of food handled every day. The team of the Italian Observatory on food losses and waste coordinated the MYWASTE-PLATE project proposal aimed to perform an initial FW assessment and diagnosis on a sample of pupils in primary schools. The challenge of MYWASTE-PLATE is to propose FW measurement with a methodology easy to use as a rapid, valid, reliable, and time-saving instrument. FW measurement will be used as a monitoring tool for the effectiveness evaluation of preventive actions aimed at reducing FW. Taking action at the school level gives the challenge to raise awareness among young generations about more sustainable food choices. The MYWASTE-PLATE team will carry out the activities with a transdisciplinary approach, gathering nutrition and biostatistics scientists, and IT communication experts, with documented experience in food waste assessment and food consumption evaluation. The project is divided into 4 Work Packages: 1) Project management and coordination; 2) Food waste measurement in school canteens with already tested and validated tools; quantification of nutrients' losses and environmental impact (e.g., greenhouse gas emissions, GHGE) of wasted foods; 3) A case study with educative intervention actions; 4) Communication strategies for users' awareness and stakeholders' sensitization. The main outcome of MYWASTE-PLATE is the provision of a pilot and demonstration protocol showing the effectiveness of FW prevention initiatives that integrate FW measurement. Policy implications and actionable recommendations will be drafted and discussed with stakeholders to embody FW prevention actions in nutritional educational strategies and evaluate the implications for the food services private sector.

Executive summary

The D1.1 "Organisation of Kick-off meeting" summarizes the outcomes and the decisions taken on the first MYWASTE-PLATE project consortium meeting that was held online on the 27th of April 2023. This report is Deliverable D1.1 related to project task 1.1 "Organization of projects meeting" of the Work Package 1 "Project Management and Coordination". The D1.1 contains a report of the main activities carried out during the kick-off meeting organized by CREA, the work plan to be carried out for each Work Package, the main issues emerging in the discussion, and the general planning of the MYWASTE-PLATE project. The kick-off meeting was originally planned in presence, however, to be more efficient and to dedicate more resources to further meetings at an advanced stage of the project, the consortium decided to perform the kick-off meeting of the MYWASTE-PLATE project online.

A total of 6 participants represented the 2 partners of MYWASTE-PLATE project.

1. Introduction

MYWASTE-PLATE project held the Kick-off meeting (KoM) as an online webinar in Rome on the 27 of April 2023. 6 participants from the 2 partner organizations (CREA and DEV4U) represented the MYWASTE-PLATE consortium. All work packages were discussed and a clear work plan for the coming two years of work was defined. The KoM was originally planned in presence, however in order to be more efficient and to dedicate more resources to the further meetings at an advanced stage of the project, the consortium decided to perform the KoM online. This decision was related to the consideration that more meetings with the schools and with the parents will be necessary at the level of project implementation, especially during the case study actions. Hence it was opted for a webinar to discuss the start-up of the project activities, the governance, and the definition of the respective responsibilities of the project participants. In addition to that after the first weeks of the project, the consortium realizes that an activity with only 2 participating entities would not need a formal meeting structure in consideration that discussion, debate, information sharing, problem-solving, and decision-making are a continuous process of the ongoing collaboration.

1.1 Organization and structure of the meeting, activities, and participants

The meeting was structured as a webinar covering half day, 27 April 2023. Actually, the KoM was carried out in an advanced stage with respect to the start-up of the activities (1 March 2023). This was done because the partners, in the first weeks of the project, worked on the development of the case study protocol (D3.1) that included the data collection tool (the school canteen questionnaire) necessary for the D2.1 – Creation of the online interface and tools. Pre-reading and analysis of all these materials was necessary before the organization of the kickoff meeting.

2. Kick-off Meeting main activities.

The content of each work package was then discussed in detail with a focus on the work plan and time to delivery. A list of actions to be taken (“to do” section) was discussed and agreed upon. In the following paragraphs, the main outcomes of this discussion were reported.

2.1 WP1 Project management and coordination (COORDINATION)

WP Leader: CREA

Objective: to establish the systems for efficient management (project management software, protocols, and formats for reporting within the management structure to the funder) and give support and directions to the partners on procedures.

T1.1 This task will be focused on the organization of official project meetings M1 (kick-off), M12, and M24 (final meeting); the organization of web conferences every month; promotion of staff visits/exchanges among partners.

In addition to the official project meetings (M1 - kick-off, M12, M24 - final meeting) other meetings will be organized with teachers in order to sensitize them for study participation, with parents as a way to return the results that will include data on waste but also general data on child attitude to foods that will be also collected (see WP2 and WP3). The project will benefit of additional meeting to explain the relevance of the activities to a large pattern of institutional stakeholders.

T1.2 A system of internal review and assessment to support informed decision-making, improve project implementation, and support the achievement of project objectives will be established. Documents will be shared on a secured collaborative internet platform provided and updated by the coordinator for knowledge management, online reporting, and information exchange, as well as email lists

Contractual obligations and expectations from EC. Presented by the Project Coordinator – Laura Rossi (CREA)

- ❖ The consortium needs to provide continuous reporting of the project through the EC portal. Deliverables must comply with the Grant Agreement (GA). Better to make a quality check before the submission of the deliverables. Deliverables cannot be submitted at any time, they are contractual obligations, and any expected delay, even minor, must be agreed upon with the Project Officer (PO) in advance of the due date, also to avoid running into ineligible costs.
- ❖ Periodic reporting: mandatory at the end of each reporting period (M12 & M24). The reports should include a description of the activities carried out during the period of implementation and must be in line with the GA; any risk incurred, and mitigation measures adopted should be mentioned.
- ❖ Acknowledgment of European Union (EU) funding: display the EU emblem NOT the EU Commission's logo (according to the GA). As communicates by the PO, the consortium was informed that "the grant agreement asks you to promote this grant and to display in all your communication/dissemination activities:
 - The following **disclaimer** (translated into a local language where appropriate): "*Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them*"; AND
 - One of the four below **EU emblem**, available at: http://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

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- ❖ The Project Coordinator (PC) should notify the Commission about news, articles, events, etc.
- ❖ Amendments: no amendment is needed for minor changes, but just for substantial issues Advise the PO before the submission for a final check. An amendment cannot be required to change the nature of the project, in this case, it would be rejected. Changes need to be reported and explained in the periodic report and in the "Use of resources" section as a deviation from Annex I with clarifications and justifications.

Reporting:

Each partner should submit:

- ❖ Periodic activity reports and financial statements at M12 & M24
- ❖ Final report and financial statement at M24

The reports will include a description of the activities performed, deliverables submitted, results reached, risks encountered (any deviation), and mitigation measures adopted.

The Project Coordinator will prepare the structure of the report both for technical and financial reporting activities that must be submitted as deliverable D1.2. The reports will be designed to be concise and informative facilitating the compilation by the partners.

The communication line will be between the PO and the PC without direct contact between the participants and the EC. Any issue should be sent to the project coordinator that could eventually refer to the EC.

Deliverables to be submitted:

D1.1 – Organization of Kick-off meeting (M2 – 30 April 2023)

D1.2 – Report formats for management support and financial reports (M3 – 31 May 2023)

To do:

- ❖ Monthly virtual meetings will be organized between the project participants.
- ❖ A table with the deadlines needs to be created and shared with the partners.
- ❖ Format of the report to be submitted as D1.2.
- ❖ Internet platform (e.g., Sharepoint) for material sharing management, online reporting, and information exchange, as well as email lists.

2.2 WP2 Food waste measurements in school canteens with WASTEPLATE (MEASUREMENTS)

WP Leader: DEV4U

Objective: to establish a user-friendly data collection system in school canteens using the already developed tool WASTEPLATE.

T2.1 Development of an electronic platform to assess food waste using the WASTEPLATE system as a validated instrument already used in school settings.

The material (a duly designed questionnaire that will be integral part of the D3.1 Case Study Protocol) for the creation of an online interface was discussed and analyzed. The possibility of having a part of the data collection on paper for very young children was proposed. A field workers team will be created that will be present during the data collection for the double purposes of checking for the data collection procedure and for testing the software. In addition to that the team on the ground will collect audio-visual material that will be used for the D4.2 – Video testimonial.

T2.2 With the procedure described in Rossi et al., (21), the CREA internal data databases will be used to obtain the nutritional composition (energy, macronutrients, micronutrients, dietary fiber) and the GHGEs values of the food wasted off. Estimation of the costs of food thrown away will be carried out based on the costs of the meals for families coupled with the increased costs of waste disposal.

The discussion on this point was focused on the data analysis system. It will be used CREA in-house software for waste nutritional composition analysis and environmental indicators analysis. The internal software is in the process of updating and will be ready for MYWASTE-PLATE analysis.

Deliverables to be submitted:

D2.1 – Creation of online interface and tools (31 August 2023)

D2.2 – Proposal for menu changes (31 August 2024)

To do:

- ❖ Selection of the schools with operative specifications (e.g., clearance for photo and video material with children)
- ❖ Evaluation of the intervention time
- ❖ Plan a meeting dedicated to the online interface analysis and discussion

2.3 WP3 Educative intervention action (CASE STUDY)

WP Leader: DEV4U

Objective: to perform a pilot scale intervention study to test the effectiveness of educative intervention using WASTEPLATE as a measurement indicator.

T3.1 In a sample of children attending the primary schools in Rome will be planned an educative intervention study to test the effectiveness of preventive actions. The sample size will be calculated using the formula of Pourhoseingholi et al. (22) with a precision level of 4% and based on the expected prevalence of waste in school canteens estimated at 30% according to Saccares et al. (20).

A large part of the discussion on WP3 was dedicated to the case study protocol. A draft of the protocol will be circulated in approximately one month (May 2023). According to the GA, two series of food waste data collection, e.g., pre and post-educative interventions approximately on October 2023 and February 2024, should be carried out. During the discussion, it was pointed out that a third data collection at the restart of schools (approximately October 2024) could be useful to evaluate the long-term impact of the educational activities. A final decision on this point will be taken at an advanced stage of the project.

T3.2 The intervention actions will be carried out with a duly designed communication strategy aimed to increase children's awareness of food waste prevention and reduction. Educational material will be in a classical format such as guidelines and posters and modern formats using the technical instruments already present in the classrooms (e.g. electronic whiteboard). Cartoons and games will be studied to increase children's participation in the actions.

A preliminary study on the existing educational materials from other similar projects was carried out. Will be produced a Communication Kit for teachers on food waste and nutritional education. Games will be produced for children differentiating the products on the basis of the different classes of ages. In addition to that printed (e.g., posters, leaflets) material will be produced for participating schools. A graphical layout to be colored will be also produced.

T3.3 The effectiveness of the food waste prevention initiative carried out in T3.1 will be done by measuring the amount of FW during the meals using WASTEPLATE as an indicator pre and post-interventions. In addition to that, an evaluation of menu acceptance and meal satisfaction will be carried out with a duly designed questionnaire.

A duly designed questionnaire was developed to evaluate the waste with the WASTEPLATE method. The questionnaire is structured in 3 sections: i) menu acceptance and meal satisfaction; ii) child neophobia and child habits in terms of breakfast and typology of snacks; iii) WASTEPLATE assessment. The section ii was added in order to contextualize the reasons for waste and to tailor the intervention actions. The final version of the questionnaire will be included in the Case Study protocol (D3.1). The structure of the questionnaire will be used to develop the on line data collection tool (D2.1).

Deliverables to be submitted:

D3.1 – Case study protocol (31 August 2023)

D3.2 – Short case study (31 August 2024)

To do:

- ❖ Draft case study protocol to be shared with consortium by May 2023.
- ❖ A duly dedicated meeting will be held for a first checking of educational materials

2.4 WP4 Communication strategies, stakeholder sensitization, and policy implications (COMMUNICATION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS)

WP Leader: CREA

Objective: to put in place a communication strategy for FW prevention and reduction in school canteens and to evaluate the policy implications of the educative interventions.

T4.1 Results of the MYWASTE-PLATE project will be used to develop recommendations for embodying FW prevention actions as part of nutritional educational activities in the school catering sector Terms of the recommendations and policy implications for school canteens users and private sectors working on food services will be shared with stakeholders and regional authorities that in Italy are the main responsible for school feeding system.

Communication and policy implications were also discussed. As a first step of communications strategies, it was decided the involvement of local authorities (e.g., the Rome Municipalities that manage a large number of school canteens) in the selection of the schools that will participate in the project. In addition to that private sector (e.g., food services responsible mainly operating in the selected schools) will be involved in the process at the very initial stages and before the data collection. Their involvement will facilitate the performance of the activities.

T4.2 A mixed modality (in the presence and online) meeting will be organized to present the methodology developed and the main findings collected. The event will be organized by the MYWASTE-PLATE research team who will participate as facilitators. The meeting will be the occasion for a participatory process with discussion groups aimed at sharing the actionable recommendations and the plans for the evolution of school canteens' preventive actions for FW reductions.

In addition to that the project has already started building stakeholder contact lists in view of the final conference (D4.3). The final conference should serve as an occasion to present results, discuss the progress of the project, and receive feedback.

Deliverables to be submitted:

D4.1 – Final report (28 February 2025)

D4.2 – Video testimonial (28 February 2025)

D4.3 – Final conference (28 February 2025)

To do:

- ❖ Formal involvement of Rome Municipality
- ❖ Formal involvement of food services actors
- ❖ Complete the stakeholder list.

Conclusions and Next Steps

Regarding the planning of next steps, the following were decided:

- ❖ All project deadlines related to deliverables and any other action will be kept updated. Consortium partners will be receiving notifications on approaching deliverables and other critical deadlines.
- ❖ Communication between consortium partners: it was decided that in addition to the scheduled, 'official' means and dates of communication, and especially for the first few months of the project,

consortium partners should be in close contact making use of teleconferencing whenever it was needed. This will be particularly important for concept clarification and data collection.

Annexes

Annex 1 – Agenda of the Kick-off meeting

Kick-off meeting agenda

Outline of the webinar (11:00-13:00)

Order	Presenter	Topic	Running Time
1.	Laura Rossi (CREA)	Welcome and Introduction to the MYWASTE-PLATE project	5 min
2	Laura Rossi (CREA)	Expectation to the European commission	5 min
3	Roundtable	Presentation of all participants	15 min
	Chair	Laura Rossi	
4	Laura Rossi (CREA)	WP1 - Project management and coordination (COORDINATION)	15 min
	Chair	Laura Rossi	
5	Dario Berardi (DEV4U) Umberto Soognamiglio (CREA) Marika Ferrari (CREA)	WP2 - Food waste measurements in school canteens with WASTEPLATE (MEASUREMENTS)	15 min
	Chair	Laura Rossi	
6	Dario Berardi (DEV4U) Umberto Soognamiglio (CREA)	WP3 - Educative Intervention action (CASE STUDY)	15 min
	Chair	Laura Rossi	
7	Laura Rossi (CREA)	WP4 - Communication strategies, stakeholder sensitization, and policy implications (COMMUNICATION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS)	15 min
	Chair	General discussion, wrap-up and close	20 min

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Annex 2 – List of participants

List of participants			
Organization	Country	Name/Surname	e-mail
CREA	Italy	Laura Rossi	Laura.rossi@crea.gov.it
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DEV4U	Italy	Sara Tomasso	Stomasso@dev4u.it

Annex 3 – Photos of the meeting

MyWaste-Plate

Kick-off meeting agenda

Outline of the webinars (11-12-13-14)

Order	Presenter	Topic	Duration
1	Laura Rossi (CREA)	Welcome and introduction to the MYWASTE-PLATE project	10 min
2	Laura Rossi (CREA)	Equilibrium to the European objectives	5 min
3	Roundtable Chair	Introduction of all participants Local Plans	15 min
4	Laura Rossi (CREA) Chair	WP1 - Project management and coordination COORDINATION	15 min
5	Chiara Merelli (DEVAL) Umberto Scrogamiglio (CREA) Marika Ferrari (CREA) Chair	WP2 - Food waste measurements in school addresses with WASTEPLATE (MEASUREMENTS) Laura Rossi	15 min
6	Daria Bernardi (DEVAL) Umberto Scrogamiglio (CREA) Chair	WP3 - Educational intervention action (CASE STUDY) Laura Rossi	15 min
7	Laura Rossi (CREA) Chair	WP4 - Communication strategies: stakeholder sensitization, and policy implications (COMMUNICATION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS) General discussion, wrap-up and close	15 min 20 min

Annex 4 – Registration of the meeting (in Italian)

Registration of the meeting in Italian is available at:

Kick-off meeting
MYWASTE-PLATE-20.

A short video of the meeting is available at:

VID-20230427-WA0
001.mp4